

Public Perception of the Impact of Climate Change on Rainfall Distribution Patterns and Agricultural Production in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Climate change is having a profound impact on rainfall patterns, imposing terrifying stresses on agricultural production, particularly in fragile regions like South South Nigeria. The present work examined the impacts of climate change, providing a timely analysis likely to inform adaptive strategies for farmers and policymakers amid growing climatic uncertainty.

Objective: The study evaluated public perception of the impact of climate change on rainfall distribution patterns and agricultural production in the South-South, Nigeria.

Method: This research employed a descriptive survey approach, drawing a random sample of 1,020 respondents, 900 crop farmers and 120 agricultural extension officers from the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, which encompasses Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers states. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire and analyzed with descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) alongside inferential testing using the t-test.

Results: The analysis identified 11 climate-related effects on rainfall patterns. Crop farmers recorded an average rating of 3.17, while extension agents averaged 3.23. The resulting p-value of 0.066 exceeded the 0.05 threshold, indicating no statistically significant difference between the two groups. A separate set of 13 climate-change impacts produced mean scores of 3.20 for farmers and 3.23 for agents, with a p-value of 0.166—again showing the difference was not significant.

Conclusion: This research concluded that crop yield instability and food insecurity problems could be addressed through multidimensional interventions, including scientific investigation, policy change, and climate-resilient agriculture.

Unique Contribution: This research provides empirical evidence-based mitigation measures of climate change on rainfall distribution patterns and agricultural production.

Key Recommendation: The government should develop and implement climate-resilient agriculture support policies, including a climate information policy, an agricultural extension policy, and a climate-smart agriculture policy.

Keywords: Climate Change, Rainfall Distribution Pattern, Agricultural Production, Effects, South-South Nigeria.

Introduction

Agriculture sits at the centre of the global economy, supplying the world with food staples, raw materials for manufacturing, and large-scale employment opportunities. The sector simultaneously advances public health, safeguards natural ecosystems, and drives economic expansion (Fasina et al., 2022). Roughly 2.5 billion people earn a livelihood from agricultural activities, underscoring the industry's critical role in poverty alleviation and food safety assurance (World Bank, 2022). Farming and its allied enterprises jointly account for about 3.5 per cent of global gross domestic product (World Bank, 2022). On the trading front, international sales of agricultural goods exceed US\$1.7 trillion annually, underscoring the sector's weight in global commerce (OECD, 2021). In Nigeria, agriculture remains pivotal, accounting for nearly 24 per cent of the national GDP and absorbing close to 70 per cent of the rural workforce, thereby reinforcing its importance for poverty reduction and food security (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). In addition to its direct economic contributions, agriculture serves as a cultural anchor, shaping cuisines, traditions, and rural identities across continents, and positioning itself as a strategic lever for achieving several Sustainable Development Goals.

Agricultural production covers the coordinated set of tasks that transform natural resources into edible products, fibres, bio-materials, and other goods required for human well-being. It spans crop cultivation, animal husbandry, aquaculture, and the harvesting of forest and wild resources, as well as the downstream operations of processing, value addition, and marketing. At its core, it represents the planned management of plant and animal systems to satisfy nutritional needs and underpin socio-economic development (Okwu & Ajayi, 2022). Besides furnishing food, agricultural production generates household income and supplies raw materials that feed domestic industries and export markets. Despite these benefits, Nigeria's farm sector confronts formidable constraints, including land degradation, infrastructure deficits, insecurity driven by conflict and banditry, limited market access, and the growing stresses of a changing climate (Ajadi, 2021).

Of all the headwinds facing modern agriculture, climate change is arguably the most pervasive and complex, exerting economic, social, ecological, and food security pressures on production systems, particularly in climate-sensitive regions. Nzeh et al. (2016) define climate change as measurable alterations in Earth's climate, driven mainly by global warming, that disrupt established atmospheric conditions. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2020) adds that such shifts encompass sustained deviations in temperature, precipitation, or sea levels, distinguishing them from short-term weather fluctuations. These interconnected changes alter natural drivers like rainfall and soil moisture, thereby reshaping the ecological foundations on which agriculture depends. Feedback loops, such as reduced soil moisture leading to higher surface temperatures, can further intensify these changes, creating cascading risks that challenge conventional farming calendars and existing extension recommendations.

The ripple effects of climate change extend far beyond temperature metrics, touching public health, farming practices, and socio-economic stability worldwide. Elevated heat exacerbates cardiovascular and respiratory ailments by intensifying air pollution and atmospheric pollen levels, while prolonged heatwaves increase heat-related exhaustion and mortality (Patel et al., 2020). Altered climatic envelopes also allow disease vectors such as mosquitoes and ticks to colonise new territories, spurring outbreaks of malaria, dengue, and other vector-borne illnesses (Watts et al., 2019). Agriculture, which remains tightly bound to weather rhythms, bears a disproportionate share of these burdens, as shifts in temperature and precipitation increasingly threaten production systems, livelihoods, and regional food supplies (IPCC, 2020). These intersecting health and climate pressures complicate agricultural labour patterns and reduce fieldwork productivity, particularly for smallholder farmers with limited adaptive capacity in the Southern part of Nigeria.

In Nigeria's South-South geopolitical zone, which comprises Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers states, the disruption is especially acute due to the region's humid tropical climate and reliance on rainfall for farming (Nwajide, 2020). While rainfall persists, its timing, intensity, and duration have become markedly erratic, with sharper swings between wet and dry phases now commonplace (Ibrahim et al., 2020). Such volatility shortens planting windows, increases the risk of flooding and prolonged dry spells, and ultimately reduces overall

crop productivity. Farmers now grapple with the dilemma of when to plant, a decision once governed by near-predictable seasonal cues.

Rainfall distribution describes how precipitation is allocated across space and through time within a given locality. Spatial distribution addresses where rain falls, whereas temporal distribution traces how amounts fluctuate daily, seasonally, and annually (Njoku & Onugwu, 2023). The resulting patterns emerge from interactions among large-scale atmospheric circulation, regional climate oscillations, and local weather dynamics (Falaiye et al., 2021). Across Nigeria, precipitation is famously uneven. In the South-South, the season typically opens in May, peaks between June and July, experiences a brief “August break,” and then resumes during September and October. Changes in rainfall onset, intensity, and duration are key indicators of climate variability, while irregularity has already driven discernible declines in yield and farm efficiency (Shi et al., 2013). Adejuwon (2020) further warns that the persistence of these extremes jeopardises national food security.

Boosting agricultural productivity in the South-South region has therefore become a double imperative: meeting the dietary needs of a growing population and enhancing resilience in the face of intensifying climate risks. Contemporary scholarship shows that altered precipitation regimes ranging from flash floods to multi-season droughts pose some of the greatest threats to yields and farm income in climate-sensitive landscapes (Wang et al., 2021). Yet evidence also suggests that targeted adaptation measures such as climate-smart agronomy, improved seed varieties, and efficient water management can offset many of these hazards, underscoring the need for region-specific assessments and interventions. Without such evidence-based planning, attempts to scale up production may inadvertently heighten exposure to climatic risks, undermining both household welfare and regional development objectives.

In South-South Nigeria, where rain-fed agriculture dominates, deviations from historical rainfall norms can devastate harvests and threaten the livelihoods of producers who depend on reliable weather calendars (IPCC, 2020). The region’s agricultural fortunes, and by extension its food-security status, are tightly linked to the timing and reliability of seasonal rains. Nonetheless, as Eze et al. (2020) point out, empirical investigations that examine how climate change is reshaping rainfall distribution and, by implication, crop output in this specific zone remain surprisingly scarce. This study, therefore, seeks to fill that gap by analysing the influence of climate variability on rainfall distribution patterns and agricultural production across Nigeria’s South-South geopolitical belt, providing evidence to inform policy and guide adaptive decision-making among farmers and extension professionals.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the impact of climate change on rainfall distribution patterns and food production in the South-South of Nigeria. In particular, the study aimed to measure the:

1. pattern of rainfall distribution in Nigeria’s South-South region;
2. impact of climate change on agricultural practice in the zone; and

3. adaptive strategies adopted by crop farmers to mitigate the adverse impact of climate change on agricultural yields.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were examined at the 0.05 significance threshold:

- H01 No statistically significant difference exists between the mean ratings of crop farmers and extension personnel regarding the influence of climate change on rainfall distribution across South-South Nigeria.
- H02 Crop farmers and extension agents do not differ significantly in their assessments of the effects of climate change on farming practices in the region.
- H03 There is no significant divergence between farmers and extension staff in their perspectives on the adaptation measures farmers employ to manage climate-induced pressures on agriculture within the South-South zone.”

Research Methodology

Design of the Study

A descriptive survey design was utilised for this study. It was conducted across the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, comprising six states: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers. This region is characterised by significant variation in rainfall distribution, with annual precipitation ranging from 2,000 mm to 4,000 mm, making it one of the most humid areas in the country (Ibrahim et al., 2020). The area experiences distinct wet and dry seasons: rainfall occurs from April to October, followed by the dry season from November to March.

Population of the Study

The study focused on a population of 1,020 farming households, comprising 900 crop farmers and 120 agricultural extension agents, randomly selected from the six states of the South-South region.

Sample Size/Sampling Technique

Given the manageable size of the population, the entire 900 crop farmers and 120 extension officers were surveyed. As no comprehensive population records of farmers and extension workers were available in the region, convenience sampling was applied in this study.

Instrument for Data Collection

Data for this study were collected using a structured questionnaire created by the researchers. The questionnaire used a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2), and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1).

Reliability/Validity of the Instrument

To ensure content validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by three academic experts from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Additionally, a pilot study was conducted in Enugu State with 30 farmers and 10 extension agents to test the instrument's reliability. The reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach's Alpha, resulting in an internal consistency value of ($\alpha = 0.85$), indicating excellent reliability.

Method of Data Collection and Analysis

The researchers and three trained assistants conducted data collection. Out of the 1,020 questionnaires distributed, 951 were returned and deemed valid for analysis. Of these, 850 responses came from crop farmers, and 101 from extension agents, while incomplete or unreturned questionnaires were excluded. The data were analysed using mean scores, standard deviations, and t-tests at a 0.05 significance level.

Presentation of Results

Table 1: Analysis of Respondents' Views on the Impact of Climate Change on Rainfall Patterns in the South-South Region of Nigeria Using Mean Ratings, Standard Deviations, and t-test

S/N	Impacts of climate change on rainfall distribution include:	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	P-value	Rmks
1.	A decrease in rainfall amounts in the region.	3.40	0.74	A	0.061	N.S
2.	Shifts in the onset and cessation dates of the rainy season.	3.09	0.78	A	0.116	N.S
3.	Increased rainfall variability in the region.	3.21	0.82	A	0.206	N.S
4.	A decrease in the number of rainy days in the region.	3.00	0.81	A	0.068	N.S
5.	Increased frequency of floods in the region.	3.10	0.89	A	0.034	N.S
6.	Increased rainfall amounts in the inland areas of the region.	3.01	0.85	A	0.062	N.S
7.	Increased frequency of droughts in the region.	3.14	0.65	A	0.311	N.S
8.	Decreased soil moisture levels in the region.	3.00	0.79	A	0.065	N.S
9.	Increased evapotranspiration rates in the region.	3.15	0.99	A	0.111	N.S
10.	Increased frequency of landslides and soil erosion in the region.	3.33	0.76	A	0.055	N.S
11.	Increased frequency of water scarcity in the region.	3.22	0.88	A	0.074	N.S

\bar{X} = Mean score; SD = Standard deviation, A=Agreed, Rmks = Remarks; Df = Degree of Freedom (947); NS= Non-Significant; N = Number of respondents (crop farmers = (N) = 850, \bar{X} = 3.17, SD = 0.78), Extension Agents = N = 101, \bar{X} = 3.23, SD = 0.80).

The results in Table 1 showed 11 items with mean scores ranging from \bar{X} = 3.00 to \bar{X} = 3.40, indicating that all items generally represent climate change impacts on rainfall distribution patterns in Nigeria's South-South region, as perceived by both crop farmers and agricultural extension agents. In addition, the standard deviations per item ranged from 0.65 to 0.99, indicating low dispersion of responses around the mean. Additionally, as presented in Table 1, the p-values for all items exceeded the 0.05 significance threshold ($P > 0.05$). This indicates that the results were not statistically significant, and H01 was therefore accepted.

Table 2: Analysis of the Impact of Climate Change on Agricultural Production in Nigeria's South-South Region Using Mean Ratings, Standard Deviations, and t-test Statistic

S/ N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Rmks	P-Value	Rmks
1.	Climate change reduces crop yields.	3.10	0.55	A	0.183	NS
2.	It alters the timing of growing seasons.	3.39	0.72	A	0.058	NS
3.	It increases the prevalence and spread of crop pests and diseases.	3.11	0.98	A	0.409	NS
4.	It exacerbates soil erosion, flooding and nutrient depletion	3.20	1.00	A	0.051	NS

5.	It leads to changes in rainfall patterns, resulting in water scarcity.	3.40	0.86	A	0.801	NS
6.	Climate-related impacts can lead to significant crop losses.	3.21	0.85	A	0.910	NS
7.	It leads to the loss of biodiversity, including crops and animals	3.20	0.63	A	0.271	NS
8.	Climate change increases the frequency of floods, damaging crops and infrastructure.	3.35	0.87	A	0.087	NS
9.	Climate change leads to droughts, reducing crop growth and agricultural production.	3.13	0.79	A	0.161	NS
10.	Climate change leads to heat stress, which affects crop growth.	3.12	0.88	A	0.057	NS
11.	Climate change alters soil temperature, affecting crop growth and productivity.	3.11	0.78	A	0.614	NS
12.	Climate change causes a reduction in farmers' income	3.21	0.79	A	0.056	NS
13.	It causes some farmers to give up farming.	3.09	0.69	A	0.511	NS

\bar{X} = Mean score; SD = Standard deviation, A=Agreed, Rmks = Remarks; Df = Degree of Freedom (947); NS= Non-Significant; N = Number of respondents (crop farmers = (N) = 850, \bar{X} = 3.20, SD = 0.81), Extension Agents = N = 101, \bar{X} = 3.23, SD = 0.85).

As shown in Table 2, the 13 items recorded mean (\bar{X}) score above the set benchmark value of 2.50; hence, this indicates respondents' consensus that climate change leads to a reduction in crop yields, alters the timing of growing seasons, among others, in Nigeria's South-South region. Consistently, no standard deviations exceeded the mark of 1.00, signifying a small amount of variability in the responses. The t-test results indicated that the p-values for all items were above the 0.05 significance level ($P > 0.05$). As a result, H_0 was accepted, suggesting that there is no significant difference in the opinions of crop farmers and agricultural extension agents on the impacts of climate change on agricultural production in Nigeria's South-South region.

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Adaptive Strategies Employed by Crop Farmers to Alleviate the Negative Effects of Climate Change on Agricultural Production

S/ N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1.	Farmers apply mulch to conserve soil moisture, control weed growth, and maintain stable soil temperatures.	3.33	0.47	A
2.	Farmers adopt climate-tolerant crop varieties that are resistant to drought, floods, and heat stress.	2.49	0.62	D
3.	Farmers diversify their crops to reduce dependence on a single crop	3.50	0.78	A
4.	Farmers adopt agroforestry practices.	3.00	1.02	A
5.	Farmers adopt conservation agriculture practices.	3.10	0.80	A
6.	The use of irrigation systems to reduce dependence on rainfall.	3.21	0.81	A
7.	Farmers insure their crops to mitigate the risks of crop failure.	2.20	0.65	D
8.	Farmers adopt integrated pest management practices.	3.45	0.78	A
9.	Farmers access climate information services, providing them with timely and accurate climate information.	2.35	0.88	D
10.	Farmers adopt crop rotation practices to improve soil fertility.	2.80	0.79	A

11.	Farmers adopt improved water harvesting techniques from rainfall and store it for irrigation purposes.	3.15	0.83	A
12.	Farmers use greenhouses to provide a controlled environment for crops.	2.11	0.77	D
13.	Farmers adopt integrated farming systems that combine crops and livestock.	3.11	0.70	A
14.	Farmers engage in extension services for improved farming.	2.09	0.88	D
15.	Farmers apply organic fertilisers like compost and manure to enhance soil fertility.	3.01	0.87	A

N = Number of respondents (crop farmers = 850, Extension Agents = 101); \bar{X} = Mean score; *SD* = Standard deviation, A= Agree, D=Disagree

Table 3 displays the results, showing that 10 out of the items had mean scores (\bar{X}) above the 2.50 threshold, indicating that the respondents agreed these 10 items represent coping strategies employed by crop farmers to reduce the adverse effects of climate change on agricultural production. Conversely, five items scored a mean below the threshold of 2.50, indicating that respondents rated these items as not part of the coping mechanisms adopted by farmers. Additionally, the standard deviation values, ranging from 0.47 to 1.02, indicated a low level of response dispersion and a high level of agreement among respondents.

Table 4: T-test Comparison of Crop Farmers and Extension Agents' Views on the Adaptation Measures for Climate Change in Agriculture in Nigeria's South-South Region

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	tcal	P-value	Remarks	Decision
Crop Farmers	850	2.87	0.78	949	-3.270	0.155	NS	Accept
Extension Agents	101	2.91	0.75					

The t-test results revealed a p-value of 0.155 and a t-value of -3.270, both of which are above the 0.05 significance level used for testing. Therefore, H_0 was retained, indicating that there is no significant difference in perceptions between crop farmers and extension agents regarding the measures farmers take to adapt to the impacts of climate change on agriculture.

Discussion of the Findings

Table 1 presents the 11 identified impacts of climate change on rainfall patterns in Nigeria's South-South region. The mean and standard deviation for crop farmers were 3.17 and 0.78, while those for agricultural extension agents were 3.23 and 0.80, respectively. These ratings demonstrate a broad consensus among both groups that climate change significantly influences rainfall in the region. The observed effects include reduced rainfall amounts, changes in intra-year rainfall statistics, heightened rainfall variability, increased rainfall extremes with lower average amounts, more frequent flood events, increased rainfall in inland areas, and more frequent drought occurrences. Additionally, the computed p-value of 0.066 at the 0.05 significance level was found to be greater than the critical value ($p > 0.05$), suggesting no significant difference in the views of crop farmers and extension agents. These results align with the findings of Ibrahim et al. (2020),

who observed similar unpredictable and extreme rainfall patterns in the South-South and other parts of Nigeria, which can lead to flooding and extended droughts. Climate change manifests through alterations in precipitation patterns (volume, intensity, and timing), leading to spatial variations in hydrology. Similarly, Falaiye et al. (2021) noted that rainfall distribution in Nigeria is irregular, with the South-South region experiencing prolonged rainy seasons. Wang et al. (2021) also noted that climate change is altering rainfall patterns, leading to both floods and prolonged droughts. Furthermore, increased rainfall exacerbates soil erosion, crop loss, and livelihood instability.

Table 2 presents the impacts of climate change on agricultural production across the South-South region, listing 13 effects. Crop farmers recorded a mean rating of 3.20 (SD = 0.81), while extension agents had a mean of 3.23 (SD = 0.85), indicating broad agreement between the groups. The impacts identified include reduced agricultural output, shortened growing seasons, increased pest and disease outbreaks, heightened soil erosion and flooding, declining soil fertility, and reduced water availability due to irregular rainfall. The difference in opinions between farmers and extension agents was not statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.166 ($p > 0.05$). These findings are consistent with the work of Oguntunde et al. (2020), who emphasised the vulnerability of rain-fed agriculture in the South-South region to climate-related disruptions such as droughts and floods. Shi et al. (2013) reported significant declines in yields of essential crops such as cassava and yams, which are vital to regional food security. IPCC (2020) similarly observed that climate change negatively impacts rain-fed farming, thereby threatening crop yields and farmers' livelihoods. In addition, Adejuwon (2020) noted that shifts in rainfall patterns had disrupted traditional planting calendars. Also, rising temperatures have led to increased pest infestations, further jeopardising crop productivity in the region.

Table 3 outlines 10 adaptive strategies employed by farmers in the South-South region to manage climate change. The average responses for crop farmers were 2.87 (SD = 0.78), and for extension agents, 2.91 (SD = 0.75). The strategies included mulching to retain soil moisture, crop diversification as a risk-management tool, agroforestry, conservation agriculture practices, and irrigation to reduce reliance on unpredictable rainfall. Furthermore, the results indicate no significant difference in the effectiveness of these strategies between crop farmers and extension agents (p-value = 0.155; $p > 0.05$). These findings are consistent with those of Oguntunde et al. (2020), who noted that farmers in the region are increasingly turning to irrigation systems to adapt to climate variability. Nwajide (2020) also found that crop diversification is widely practised as a resilience strategy, with farmers growing a variety of crops, including cassava, maize, and yams. Uchendu and Asuquo (2021) reported that conservation agriculture practices, including minimal tillage, crop rotation, and cover cropping, improve soil health and moisture retention. This approach helps reduce soil erosion and increases the soil's ability to withstand climate stress. Moreover, Adejuwon (2020) highlighted the importance of mulching in combating poor crop yields and soil degradation resulting from climate change.

Conclusion

The study provides valuable insights into the complex connection between climate variability and agricultural productivity in Nigeria's South-South region, which is highly dependent on agriculture

for both economic stability and food security. The findings indicate a discernible alteration in rainfall distribution patterns characterised by increased irregularity, prolonged dry spells, and intensified rainfall events. These changes pose severe implications for agricultural production, including crop yield variability, heightened vulnerability to pests and diseases, and threats to food security. In conclusion, addressing the effects of climate change on rainfall distribution and agricultural production in South-South Nigeria requires a multifaceted approach that integrates scientific research, policy reform, and hands-on climate-resilient farming practices.

Recommendations

1. The government and relevant stakeholders should encourage and facilitate the adoption of climate-resilient farming techniques, such as conservation agriculture, agroforestry, and irrigation, to help minimise farmers' exposure to climate change risks.
2. The government should formulate and develop policies supporting climate-resilient agriculture, such as climate information policy, agricultural extension policy and climate-smart agriculture policy.
3. The government should invest in advanced meteorological services and technology to improve weather forecasting accuracy, as well as establish a reliable early warning system for adverse weather conditions to help farmers make informed decisions.
4. In the South-South region, climate-resilient agriculture should be enabled by better coordination and collaboration between the government, research institutes, farmers' organisations, and other stakeholders.

Suggestions for Future Studies

The following recommendations are proposed for further investigation:

1. The Contribution of Indigenous Knowledge in Reducing the Effects of Climate Change on Agricultural Production in Nigeria's South-South Region
2. The Contributions of Extension Agents to Mitigating Agricultural Climate Change
3. Economic Evaluation of Climate Change Effects on Agricultural Productivity and Food Security in Nigeria's North-East Region

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